

Tax Compliance And The Manufacturing Sector Output In Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

This study investigates the impact of tax compliance on the growth of Nigeria's manufacturing sector, using key tax compliance proxies such as Tax Compliance Rate (TCR), Tax Effort Index (TEI), Tax Gap (TG), Time Taken for Tax Compliance (TTTC), and Tax Audit Yield (TAY) to evaluate their effect on Manufacturing Sector Output Growth Rate (MSOGR). The study adopts a quantitative, explanatory research design to explore the causal relationships between these variables. The research utilizes secondary data spanning from 1999 to 2024, collected from the Federal Inland Revenue Service (FIRS), the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN), and the National Bureau of Statistics (NBS). The analysis, conducted using combination of preliminary, diagnostic, and inferential tests to examine the impact of tax compliance measures on the manufacturing sector's output in Nigeria. These tests include descriptive statistics, correlation analysis, variance inflation factors (VIF), the Jarque-Bera probability test, the Breusch-Godfrey serial correlation LM test, the Breusch-Pagan-Godfrey heteroskedasticity test, the Ramsey RESET test, the group unit root test, the Johansen cointegration test, and the ordinary least squares (OLS) multiple regression analysis, reveals varied impacts of tax compliance measures on manufacturing output growth. Findings show that TCR and TTTC have no statistically significant impact on MSOGR, while TEI, TG, and TAY have a significant positive effect on MSOGR. The study concludes that tax compliance is critical to fostering growth in Nigeria's manufacturing sector and recommends that the Nigerian government should focus on increasing tax efforts, particularly by improving tax collection efficiency and enforcement measures. Strengthening the tax administration system can enhance manufacturing sector output.

Keywords: Tax Compliance, Tax Compliance Rate, Tax Effort Index, Tax Gap, Tax Compliance, Tax Audit Yield and Manufacturing Sector Output Growth Rate.

INTRODUCTION

Tax compliance is a vital component of fiscal policy, influencing economic development and shaping the performance of Nigeria's manufacturing sector. Compliance is often measured through indicators such as the Tax Compliance Rate (TCR), Tax Effort Index (TEI), Tax Gap (TG), Time Taken for Tax

Compliance (TTTC), and Tax Audit Yield (TAY), while sectoral performance is captured by the Manufacturing Sector Output Growth Rate (MSOGR). Understanding this relationship is essential for designing policies that balance revenue generation with industrial growth (Adebisi & Gbegi, 2023). The Nigerian manufacturing sector has long been central to GDP and employment, yet it faces challenges including infrastructure deficits, policy inconsistencies, and a complex tax system. In the first half of 2023, the sector contributed ₦606.7 billion in taxes—17.4% of federal revenue (National Bureau of Statistics, 2023). Despite this significant share, inefficiencies in tax administration hinder competitiveness and investment. The TCR, reflecting the proportion of taxpayers fulfilling obligations, remains low in Nigeria due to complicated procedures, weak enforcement, and limited trust in government spending (Okoye & Ezejiofor, 2022). This undermines revenue mobilization and compels the state to borrow or raise rates, raising costs for manufacturers. The TEI, which measures actual revenue against potential, is also weak, reflecting systemic inefficiencies and overdependence on indirect taxes that disproportionately burden manufacturers (Uadiale et al., 2023). A substantial TG—the gap between potential and actual revenue—further limits infrastructure financing critical to industrial growth (Fagbemi et al., 2022). The TTTC imposes additional burdens, as firms expend significant time navigating complex tax procedures. Lengthy filing, audits, and administrative hurdles increase costs and reduce competitiveness. Streamlining through digitalization and simplification can reduce compliance burdens and foster a more business-friendly environment (Owolabi & Okwu, 2023). Similarly, while TAY—additional revenue from audits—helps deter evasion, overly aggressive enforcement creates adversarial relationships, deterring compliance and straining manufacturers (Ibadin & Eiya, 2023).

The multiplicity of taxes compounds these challenges. Nigerian manufacturers contend with more than 30 different levies, and proposals for 18 new taxes further raise concerns (Manufacturers Association of Nigeria, 2023). Such a fragmented regime stifles investment and weakens global competitiveness. Empirical evidence highlights this tension. Eniekezimene et al. (2024) found that company income tax and import VAT negatively affected manufacturing output, while domestic VAT had positive long-run effects. Sakanko et al. (2022) similarly observed that CIT and import taxes stimulated output, whereas VAT constrained growth. These findings underscore the need for a balanced tax policy that encourages compliance without overburdening manufacturers. Beyond administration, perceptions of fairness and service delivery influence compliance. When taxpayers believe contributions are mismanaged or fail to yield visible public benefits, willingness to comply diminishes (Adegbite & Olayemi, 2023). Transparency, efficient service delivery, and visible infrastructure improvements can strengthen trust and compliance. Despite extensive research linking taxation to growth, gaps remain in understanding how compliance specifically affects Nigeria's manufacturing sector. Few studies have integrated multiple compliance measures, while recent digital tax reforms remain underexplored (Nwachukwu et al., 2024). This study addresses these gaps by examining how TCR, TEI, TG, TTTC, and TAY jointly affect MSOGR, offering evidence for tax reforms that can enhance compliance, reduce burdens, and promote industrial growth.

Review of Related Literature

Conceptual Review

Tax Compliance

Tax compliance is central to sustainable economic development, particularly for revenue generation and industrial growth. In Nigeria, the manufacturing sector—vital for GDP and employment—faces persistent challenges due to inefficiencies in the tax system. While a sound compliance framework fosters growth through predictability (Adebisi & Gbegi, 2023; Okoye & Ezejiofor, 2022), Nigeria's system suffers from multiple taxation, bureaucratic bottlenecks, and inconsistencies that weaken manufacturing output (Uadiale et al., 2023; Fagbemi et al., 2022). The Tax Compliance Rate (TCR) remains low due to distrust, corruption, and cumbersome filing, translating into revenue losses and limiting infrastructure investment (Bello & Akinola, 2023; Ojo & Ajibade, 2024). The Tax Effort Index (TEI) also reflects inefficiency, with overreliance on indirect taxes that disproportionately burden manufacturers and deter investment

(Uadiale et al., 2023). Similarly, a wide Tax Gap (TG) from evasion reduces resources for industrial support, while closing the gap could significantly enhance revenue (Ahmed & Yusuf, 2023). Time Taken for Tax Compliance (TTTC) is high, diverting resources from production and weakening competitiveness. Simplification and digitalization can reduce this burden (Owolabi & Okwu, 2023). Tax Audit Yield (TAY), while important, often imposes multiple audits that strain manufacturers. Balanced enforcement with education is needed.

Manufacturing Sector Output

The manufacturing sector is vital to economic development, driving employment, industrialization, and GDP growth. In Nigeria, however, the sector remains constrained by structural and policy challenges. The Manufacturing Sector Output Growth Rate (MSOGR) is a key indicator of its performance, yet Nigeria's contribution to GDP averages only 8–10%, far below other emerging economies (Ajayi & Ogunleye, 2022). High production costs, poor infrastructure, and regulatory bottlenecks have weakened growth. Inefficient electricity supply forces firms to rely on costly alternatives, while dependence on imported raw materials makes manufacturers vulnerable to exchange rate instability, increasing costs and deterring investment (Nwachukwu et al., 2023; Okafor & Chukwuma, 2022). Limited access to credit due to high interest rates further constrains expansion (Olatunji & Bello, 2023). Policy inconsistencies and multiple taxation reduce profit margins, discouraging reinvestment (Adegbite & Yusuf, 2024). Poor transport and port infrastructure raise logistics costs, while inflation erodes purchasing power and inflates production costs (Eze & Ugochukwu, 2022). Outdated technology also undermines efficiency, leaving Nigerian manufacturers uncompetitive compared to global peers (Balogun & Afolabi, 2023). Trade policies and global competition further complicate performance (Usman & Ibrahim, 2024). Scholars emphasize reforms in infrastructure, credit access, industrial policy, and digital transformation as critical to improving MSOGR (Kolawole & Akinyemi, 2024). Without such reforms, growth potential will remain unrealized.

Theoretical Review

The two theories relevant to the impact of tax compliance (proxied by Tax Compliance Rate (TCR), Tax Effort Index (TEI), Tax Gap (TG), Time Taken for Tax Compliance (TTTC), and Tax Audit Yield (TAY)) on manufacturing sector output (proxied by Manufacturing Sector Output Growth Rate (MSOGR)) in Nigeria:

The Ability-to-Pay Theory of Taxation

The Ability-to-Pay Theory of Taxation, rooted in Adam Smith (1776) and refined by Musgrave (1959), posits that taxes should be levied according to financial capacity, ensuring fairness and preventing excessive burdens. In Nigeria, where compliance remains weak, the theory provides a useful framework for assessing how tax compliance indicators; Tax Compliance Rate (TCR), Tax Effort Index (TEI), Tax Gap (TG), Time Taken for Tax Compliance (TTTC), and Tax Audit Yield (TAY) affect manufacturing sector output (MSOGR). Nigeria's low TCR reflects distrust, high tax burdens, and administrative inefficiencies, widening the TG and reducing revenues for infrastructure (Adebisi & Gbegi, 2023; Bello & Akinola, 2023). A low TEI signals inefficiencies and overreliance on indirect taxes that disproportionately affect manufacturers (Uadiale et al., 2023). High TTTC diverts resources from production, while excessive audits under TAY increase costs and discourage investment (Ojo & Ajibade, 2024). By aligning tax policies with the Ability-to-Pay principle—through fairer rates, simplified compliance, and balanced enforcement—Nigeria can improve compliance, close revenue gaps, and strengthen manufacturing sector growth.

The Cost of Compliance Theory

The Cost of Compliance Theory posits that the expenses of fulfilling tax obligations—monetary, administrative, and opportunity costs—significantly influence taxpayer behavior (Allingham & Sandmo, 2020). High compliance costs often reduce willingness to comply, leading to evasion and lower government revenue. In Nigeria, tax compliance, proxied by Tax Compliance Rate (TCR), Tax Effort Index (TEI), Tax Gap (TG), Time Taken for Tax Compliance (TTTC), and Tax Audit Yield (TAY),

directly impacts manufacturing sector performance, measured by Manufacturing Sector Output Growth Rate (MSOGR) (Bello & Akinola, 2021). When compliance costs are high, businesses divert resources from production to administration, lowering TCR and widening the TG (Nwachukwu et al., 2023; Fagbemi et al., 2022). Nigeria's low TEI reflects inefficiencies linked to cumbersome filing, multiple taxation, and policy inconsistency (Owolabi & Okwu, 2023). Excessive TTTC and frequent audits further strain manufacturers, discouraging investment (Ojo & Ajibade, 2024). Reducing compliance costs through digitalization, streamlined procedures, and balanced audits can improve compliance, close the tax gap, and enhance MSOGR, fostering sustainable industrial growth (Ahmed & Yusuf, 2023).

Empirical Review

Tax compliance and its effect on manufacturing sector output has been extensively studied, with particular attention to Nigeria. Proxies such as Tax Compliance Rate (TCR), Tax Effort Index (TEI), Tax Gap (TG), Time Taken for Tax Compliance (TTTC), and Tax Audit Yield (TAY) are central in explaining sectoral performance, often measured by Manufacturing Sector Output Growth Rate (MSOGR).

Bello et al. (2024) analyzed TCR and TEI using data from 150 firms and FIRS reports (2019–2023). Results from OLS regression showed that higher TCR significantly boosted manufacturing output, concluding that transparent, business-friendly tax systems improve sectoral productivity. Similarly, Nwogugu et al. (2024), using data from 120 firms, found that improvements in TEI positively impacted profitability and output, recommending stronger tax education.

Nwachukwu et al. (2024) examined TTTC using data from 250 companies. They reported that excessive time spent on compliance reduced operational efficiency and output, recommending streamlined tax processes. Owolabi and Okwu (2023), using ARDL analysis of NBS and FIRS data (2012–2022), reached similar conclusions, showing that reducing TTTC would significantly improve sectoral productivity.

Adebisi and Gbegi (2023) assessed TCR and tax audits using regression analysis on 200 firms (2017–2022). Their findings showed that compliance and effective audits significantly enhanced manufacturing growth, leading to recommendations for stronger enforcement mechanisms. Likewise, Ibadin and Eiya (2023), using a case study of 200 firms (2019–2023), revealed that higher TAY increased output but warned that excessive audits created inefficiencies, urging balanced enforcement.

Bello and Akinola (2023) investigated TG using FIRS and industry data (2018–2022). Their results showed that a wide tax gap negatively affected manufacturing output, discouraging compliance. They recommended closing the gap through better enforcement and transparent systems. Okoye and Ezejiofor (2022) also highlighted the negative impact of TG, showing that a larger gap reduced productivity, while improvements in TEI boosted sectoral performance.

Uadiale et al. (2023) adopted a longitudinal design (2015–2022) and found that compliance measures, particularly TCR and TAY, positively correlated with output, suggesting that consistent compliance boosts productivity. Ahmed and Yusuf (2023), using mixed methods on 100 firms (2017–2022), also found that high TCR and efficient audits directly enhanced manufacturing growth.

Fagbemi et al. (2022) examined TEI using a mixed-methods approach (2016–2022). Their findings showed that higher TEI boosted output, while inefficiencies in collection and administration hindered growth. They emphasized incentives and improved training for tax officers.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This study examines the impact of tax compliance on manufacturing sector output in Nigeria, with emphasis on how compliance indicators influence the Manufacturing Sector Output Growth Rate (MSOGR). A quantitative, explanatory research design was adopted to test hypotheses and establish causal relationships using numerical data. Secondary data were exclusively relied upon, sourced from the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN), the Federal Inland Revenue Service (FIRS), and the National Bureau of Statistics (NBS). The population comprises all manufacturing firms in Nigeria, but purposive sampling was used to focus on sectors with consistent data between 1999 and 2024. This period was chosen to

capture the effects of tax reforms, fiscal policy changes, and industrial developments. Tax compliance proxies included the Tax Compliance Rate (TCR), Tax Effort Index (TEI), Tax Gap (TG), Time Taken for Tax Compliance (TTTC), and Tax Audit Yield (TAY). Data on sectoral output were obtained from NBS and CBN reports. Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) regression was employed to estimate the effect of compliance indicators on MSOGR. The analysis was carried out using E-Views 9.0, beginning with descriptive statistics before regression estimation. Several diagnostic tests were applied to ensure robustness, including the Augmented Dickey-Fuller test for stationarity, Johansen cointegration for long-run relationships, the Variance Inflation Factor for multicollinearity, Breusch-Pagan for heteroscedasticity, and the Durbin-Watson statistic for autocorrelation. By combining reliable data sources, purposive sampling, OLS regression, and diagnostic checks, this methodology provides credible insights into how tax compliance influences Nigeria’s manufacturing performance and offers evidence for policy reforms. The model specification for the study is as follows:

$$MSOGR_t = \beta_0 + \beta_1TCR_t + \beta_2TEI_t + \beta_3TG_t + \beta_4TTTC_t + \beta_5TAY_t + \epsilon_t$$

Where:

MSOGR = Manufacturing Sector Output Growth Rate (dependent variable)

TCR = Tax Compliance Rate (independent variable)

TEI = Tax Effort Index (independent variable)

TG = Tax Gap (independent variable)

TTTC = Time Taken for Tax Compliance (independent variable)

TAY = Tax Audit Yield (independent variable)

ϵ_t = Error term.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Data Presentation

This section dealt with data presentations on tax compliance proxied with Tax Compliance Rate (TCR), Tax Effort Index (TEI), Tax Gap (TG), Time Taken for Tax Compliance (TTTC) and Tax Audit Yield (TAY) and manufacturing sector output proxied with Manufacturing Sector Output Growth Rate (MSOGR) in Nigeria.

Descriptive Statistics

Descriptive statistics provide a preliminary understanding of the dataset by summarizing key statistical measures such as the mean, standard deviation, minimum, and maximum values of the variables. This test helps to identify potential outliers, data inconsistencies, and the overall distribution of the dataset before conducting further econometric analyses. This presented in Table 1 below:

Table 1: Descriptive Statistics

	MSOGR	TCR	TEI	TG	TTTC	TAY
Mean	4.005128	68.16176	53.53032	14.81228	190.0920	46.39893
Median	2.012448	66.12970	55.23528	14.31373	196.6011	46.25224
Maximum	14.71301	88.79639	78.47923	24.73774	277.4425	66.48488
Minimum	-4.262261	50.82338	31.71943	5.110442	105.0838	20.34761
Std. Dev.	5.935572	11.50003	15.45266	6.662114	52.93607	15.70121
Skewness	0.643600	0.298390	0.165033	-0.001306	-0.121901	-0.130171
Kurtosis	2.243869	1.865892	1.780179	1.454063	1.906860	1.462185
Jarque-Bera	2.414336	1.779211	1.729983	2.589087	1.358928	2.635375
Probability	0.299043	0.410818	0.421055	0.274023	0.506889	0.267754
Observations	26	26	26	26	26	26

Source: EVIEW 9.0 Output, 2025.

The descriptive statistics revealed key patterns in Nigeria’s tax compliance and manufacturing sector output. The Manufacturing Sector Output Growth Rate (MSOGR) averaged 4.01%, reflecting moderate growth with notable fluctuations, ranging from -4.26% contraction to 14.71% expansion. Tax Compliance Rate (TCR) averaged 68.16%, suggesting moderate adherence, though variability was evident, with compliance ranging between 50.82% and 88.79%. The Tax Effort Index (TEI) averaged 53.53%, indicating that just over half of potential revenues were collected, with values spanning 31.71% to 78.47%. The Tax Gap (TG) averaged 14.81%, reflecting persistent revenue leakages despite some years of lower shortfalls. Time Taken for Tax Compliance (TTTC) was high, averaging 190.09 hours, indicating significant administrative burdens on businesses. Tax Audit Yield (TAY) averaged 46.39%, showing moderate effectiveness in revenue recovery. Most variables followed near-normal distributions, though flatter than normal. Overall, findings highlight inefficiencies in compliance processes, revenue mobilization, and enforcement, with implications for manufacturing growth.

Correlation Analysis

Correlation analysis measures the strength and direction of relationships between independent and dependent variables. It helps in identifying potential multicollinearity issues, which occur when independent variables are highly correlated with each other. High correlation between predictors can distort regression estimates, making it difficult to isolate the impact of individual variables on the dependent variable. This presented in Table 2 below:

Table 2: Correlation Analysis

	MSOGR	TCR	TEI	TG	TTTC	TAY
MSOGR	1.000000					
TCR	-0.052188	1.000000				
TEI	0.209633	0.351330	1.000000			
TG	0.255362	-0.011492	0.058955	1.000000		
TTTC	-0.015458	-0.099326	-0.100174	0.078460	1.000000	
TAY	0.122967	0.134239	-0.169640	0.189659	0.366893	1.000000

Source: EVIEW 9.0 Output, 2025.

The correlation analysis in Table 2 examines the relationship between MSOGR and the independent variables TCR, TEI, TG, TTTC, and TAY. The correlation of -0.0522 between TCR and MSOGR indicates a very weak negative relationship, suggesting that higher compliance may slightly reduce growth due to added cost burdens, though the effect is negligible. TEI shows a weak positive correlation of 0.2096 with MSOGR, implying that improved efficiency in collection is mildly associated with higher growth. TG records a weak to moderate positive correlation of 0.2554, meaning higher uncollected revenue sometimes coincides with growth, possibly because firms retain more income, though long-term effects may be adverse. TTTC has a correlation of -0.0155 with MSOGR, showing almost no relationship. TAY demonstrates a weak positive correlation of 0.1230 with MSOGR, reflecting slight benefits from improved enforcement. Overall, tax compliance variables show only weak effects, with other structural factors likely driving growth.

Variance Inflation Factors (VIF)

Variance inflation factors (VIF) quantify the severity of multicollinearity in the regression model. A high VIF value indicates that a predictor variable is highly correlated with other independent variables, leading to unreliable coefficient estimates. If multicollinearity is detected, remedial actions such as dropping redundant variables or applying principal component analysis (PCA) may be necessary to improve the model's efficiency. This presented in Table 3 below:

Table 3: Variance Inflation Factors (VIF)

Variance Inflation Factors
 Date: 04/01/25 Time: 17:43
 Sample: 1999 2024
 Included observations: 26

Variable	Coefficient Variance	Uncentered VIF	Centered VIF
C	92.35502	63.18209	NA
TCR	0.014157	46.22852	1.231590
TEI	0.007794	16.50372	1.224281
TG	0.036081	6.469168	1.053428
TTTC	0.000644	17.10517	1.186961
TAY	0.008089	13.22554	1.311793

Source: EVIEW 9.0 Output, 2025.

In Table 3, VIF values were used to test for multicollinearity in the regression model. The results show no variable exceeds the common threshold of 5, confirming that multicollinearity is not an issue. The VIF of 1.2316 for TCR indicates statistical independence, with little risk of redundancy in the model. TEI records a VIF of 1.2243, also demonstrating low correlation with other predictors. TG has the lowest VIF at 1.0534, confirming minimal overlap and strong independence. TTTC shows a VIF of 1.1870, indicating no concern of collinearity with the other tax variables. TAY, with the highest VIF of 1.3118, remains well below critical levels, meaning its inclusion does not distort coefficient estimates. Overall, the low VIF values confirm that all variables; TCR, TEI, TG, TTTC, and TAY are sufficiently independent, ensuring stable regression results. The model can therefore proceed confidently with OLS estimation, residual diagnostics, and hypothesis testing.

Jarque-Bera Probability Test

The Jarque-Bera test examines whether the residuals of the regression model follow a normal distribution. Many econometric techniques, including hypothesis testing and confidence interval estimation, assume normally distributed residuals. If the residuals deviate significantly from normality, the presence of outliers or non-linearity may require further investigation and model adjustments. This presented in Table 4.5 below:

Table 4: Jarque-Bera Probability Test

Source: EVIEW 9.0 Output, 2025.

In Table 4, the JB test is applied to assess whether the dataset follows a normal distribution by evaluating skewness and kurtosis. The test statistic follows a χ^2 distribution with two degrees of freedom, and the decision rule depends on the p-value. When the p-value exceeds 0.05, the null hypothesis of normality cannot be rejected, meaning the data is normally distributed. Conversely, a p-value below 0.05 suggests significant deviation from normality. If most variables record p-values above 0.05, the dataset meets the

assumptions of OLS regression, and no major transformations are needed. However, when several variables fall below the threshold, the data may display skewness or kurtosis issues, requiring remedies such as log transformations or robust regression techniques to ensure model accuracy. The JB test therefore serves as an important diagnostic tool for confirming dataset suitability for OLS regression and guiding corrective actions when normality assumptions are violated.

Breusch-Godfrey Serial Correlation LM Test

The Breusch-Godfrey test assesses the presence of serial correlation (autocorrelation) in the residuals of a regression model. Serial correlation violates the assumption of independence among error terms, leading to inefficient and biased parameter estimates. Detecting and correcting for serial correlation ensures that standard errors are accurately estimated, preventing misleading statistical inferences. This presented in Table 5 below:

Table 5: Breusch-Godfrey Serial Correlation LM Test

Breusch-Godfrey Serial Correlation LM Test:

F-statistic	2.767797	Prob. F(2,18)	0.0895
Obs*R-squared	10.15224	Prob. Chi-Square(2)	0.0870

Source: EVIEW 9.0 Output, 2025.

In Table 5, the Breusch-Godfrey LM test is applied to detect autocorrelation in regression residuals. Autocorrelation occurs when residuals from different time periods are correlated, violating the OLS assumption of independence. The decision rule is based on p-values: if above 0.05, we fail to reject the null hypothesis, indicating no significant serial correlation; if below 0.05, serial correlation is present. The F-statistic (2.767797) and Obs*R-squared (10.15224) provide measures of correlation strength. Prob. F(2,18) = 0.0895 and Prob. Chi-Square(2) = 0.0870, both above 0.05, indicate failure to reject the null hypothesis. Thus, there is no evidence of serial correlation in the model’s residuals. This confirms that the regression satisfies the OLS assumption of uncorrelated errors, ensuring coefficient estimates are efficient and unbiased. Consequently, corrective measures such as GLS or Newey-West adjustments are unnecessary. The absence of serial correlation strengthens the reliability of the estimated relationship between tax compliance and MSOGR in Nigeria.

Heteroskedasticity Test: Breusch-Pagan-Godfrey

The Breusch-Pagan-Godfrey test detects heteroskedasticity, a condition where the variance of the residuals is not constant across observations. Heteroskedasticity violates the assumption of homoscedasticity in OLS regression, leading to inefficient estimators and incorrect statistical inferences. If heteroskedasticity is present, robust standard errors or generalized least squares (GLS) estimation methods may be used to correct for it. This presented in Table 6 below:

Table 6: Heteroskedasticity Test: Breusch-Pagan-Godfrey

Heteroskedasticity Test: Breusch-Pagan-Godfrey

F-statistic	1.363325	Prob. F(5,20)	0.2796
Obs*R-squared	6.609043	Prob. Chi-Square(5)	0.2514
Scaled explained SS	2.191340	Prob. Chi-Square(5)	0.8221

Source: EVIEW 9.0 Output, 2025.

In Table 6, the Breusch-Pagan-Godfrey test is applied to check heteroskedasticity in the regression model. Heteroskedasticity occurs when error variances are not constant, violating the OLS assumption of homoskedasticity. The decision rule is that if p-values (Prob. F, Prob. Chi-Square, and Scaled Explained SS) exceed 0.05, the null hypothesis is not rejected, indicating no heteroskedasticity; if below 0.05, heteroskedasticity exists. The results show F-statistic = 1.363325, Obs*R-squared = 6.609043, and Scaled Explained SS = 2.191340. The probability values are Prob. F(5,20) = 0.2796, Prob. Chi-Square(5) = 0.2514, and Prob. Scaled Explained SS = 0.8221. Since all values are greater than 0.05, the null hypothesis is retained, indicating no significant heteroskedasticity in the residuals. This confirms that the OLS assumption of constant variance holds, ensuring efficient and unbiased coefficient estimates. No

remedial adjustments such as robust errors or GLS are necessary, and the model's findings on tax compliance and MSOGR remain statistically valid.

Ramsey RESET Test

The Ramsey RESET test evaluates whether the regression model is correctly specified by detecting functional form misspecifications. If a model is misspecified (e.g., omitting key variables or using incorrect functional forms), the estimated coefficients may be biased. The test helps confirm whether the model adequately captures the underlying economic relationships or requires further refinement. This presented in Table 7 below:

Table 7: Ramsey RESET Test

Ramsey RESET Test
Equation: UNTITLED
Specification: MSOGR C TCR TEI TG TTTC TAY
Omitted Variables: Squares of fitted values

	Value	Df	Probability
t-statistic	0.458041	19	0.6521
F-statistic	0.209802	(1, 19)	0.6521
Likelihood ratio	0.285524	1	0.5931

Source: EVIEW 9.0 Output, 2025.

In Table 7, the Ramsey RESET test is applied to check whether the regression model is correctly specified or suffers from omitted variables, incorrect functional forms, or non-linearity. The decision rule is that if the p-value exceeds 0.05, we fail to reject H_0 , meaning no specification errors; if below 0.05, H_0 is rejected, indicating misspecification. Results show t-statistic = 0.458041 (p-value = 0.6521), F-statistic = 0.209802 (p-value = 0.6521), and Likelihood Ratio = 0.285524 (p-value = 0.5931). Since all p-values are above 0.05, the null hypothesis is retained, confirming the model is correctly specified. This means that adding squared fitted values does not significantly improve the regression, and there is no strong evidence of functional form errors. By implication, the regression model examining the effect of tax compliance measures on MSOGR is well-specified. The OLS estimates remain valid, reliable, and free from specification bias.

Group Unit Root Test

The group unit root test examines whether time-series variables in a panel dataset are stationary or contain unit roots. If a variable is non-stationary, using it in regression without differencing can lead to spurious results. This test is crucial for determining the appropriate transformations (such as first-differencing or log transformations) before proceeding with regression analysis. This presented in Table 8 below:

Table 8: Group Unit Root Test

Group unit root test: Summary
Series: MSOGR, TCR, TEI, TG, TTTC, TAY
Date: 04/01/25 Time: 18:03
Sample: 1999 2024
Exogenous variables: Individual effects
Automatic selection of maximum lags
Automatic lag length selection based on SIC: 0
Newey-West automatic bandwidth selection and Bartlett kernel
Balanced observations for each test

Method	Statistic	Prob.**	Cross-sections	Obs
Null: Unit root (assumes common unit root process)				
Levin, Lin & Chu t*	-8.88244	0.0000	6	150
Null: Unit root (assumes individual unit root process)				
Im, Pesaran and Shin W-stat	-8.35152	0.0000	6	150
ADF - Fisher Chi-square	79.7970	0.0000	6	150
PP - Fisher Chi-square	79.9818	0.0000	6	150

** Probabilities for Fisher tests are computed using an asymptotic Chi-square distribution. All other tests assume asymptotic normality.

Source: EVIEW 9.0 Output, 2025.

In Table 8, the Group Unit Root Test assesses whether the study variables are stationary or contain a unit root. Stationarity is essential to avoid spurious regressions. Results show Levin, Lin & Chu $t = -8.88244$ (p-value = 0.0000), indicating stationarity under a common process. Im, Pesaran and Shin $W\text{-stat} = -8.35152$ (p-value = 0.0000) also confirms stationarity when allowing individual unit root processes. ADF-Fisher Chi-square = 79.7970 (p-value = 0.0000) rejects the null of a unit root, while PP-Fisher Chi-square = 79.9818 (p-value = 0.0000) further validates stationarity after adjusting for heteroskedasticity and autocorrelation. Since all p-values are below 0.05, the null hypothesis of a unit root is rejected, meaning all variables are stationary at level $I(0)$. This allows direct application of OLS regression and cointegration analysis without differencing. By implication, the model results are reliable, and the next step involves Johansen Cointegration Test to check long-run relationships.

Johansen Cointegration Test

The Johansen cointegration test investigates whether long-run equilibrium relationships exist between the dependent and independent variables. If variables are found to be cointegrated, it implies that they share a stable long-term relationship despite short-term fluctuations. The presence of cointegration justifies the use of long-run regression models such as the error correction model (ECM). This presented in Table 9 below:

Table 9: Johansen Cointegration Test

Date: 04/01/25 Time: 18:03
 Sample (adjusted): 2001 2024
 Included observations: 24 after adjustments
 Trend assumption: Linear deterministic trend
 Series: MSOGR TCR TEI TG TTTC TAY
 Lags interval (in first differences): 1 to 1
 Unrestricted Cointegration Rank Test (Trace)

Hypothesized No. of CE(s)	Eigenvalue	Trace Statistic	0.05 Critical Value	Prob.**
None *	0.886339	126.1033	95.75366	0.0001
At most 1 *	0.700582	73.91442	69.81889	0.0227
At most 2	0.520967	44.97245	47.85613	0.0910
At most 3	0.401950	27.30878	29.79707	0.0943
At most 4	0.325387	14.97084	15.49471	0.0598
At most 5 *	0.205601	5.524066	3.841466	0.0187

Trace test indicates 2 cointegrating eqn(s) at the 0.05 level

* denotes rejection of the hypothesis at the 0.05 level

**MacKinnon-Haug-Michelis (1999) p-values

Unrestricted Cointegration Rank Test (Maximum Eigenvalue)

Hypothesized No. of CE(s)	Eigenvalue	Max-Eigen Statistic	0.05 Critical Value	Prob.**
None *	0.886339	52.18890	40.07757	0.0014
At most 1	0.700582	28.94197	33.87687	0.1734
At most 2	0.520967	17.66367	27.58434	0.5233
At most 3	0.401950	12.33793	21.13162	0.5147
At most 4	0.325387	9.446778	14.26460	0.2509
At most 5 *	0.205601	5.524066	3.841466	0.0187

Max-eigenvalue test indicates 1 cointegrating eqn(s) at the 0.05 level

* denotes rejection of the hypothesis at the 0.05 level

**MacKinnon-Haug-Michelis (1999) p-values

Source: EVIEW 9.0 Output, 2025.

In Table 9, the Johansen Cointegration Test evaluates whether long-run relationships exist among MSOGR, TCR, TEI, TG, TTTC, and TAY. The Trace test shows strong evidence of cointegration: for None, Eigenvalue = 0.886339, Trace Statistic = 126.1033, $p = 0.0001$, rejecting no cointegration; for At most 1, Eigenvalue = 0.700582, Trace Statistic = 73.91442, $p = 0.0227$, confirming at least one cointegrating vector. Beyond this, p-values above 0.05 suggest no additional cointegration. Overall, the Trace test identifies two cointegrating equations. The Maximum Eigenvalue test supports one cointegrating relationship: None, Eigenvalue = 0.886339, Max-Eigen Statistic = 52.18890, $p = 0.0014$ rejects the null, while At most 1, with $p = 0.1734$, fails to reject further cointegration. Together, results confirm long-run equilibrium among variables. The Trace test points to two relationships, while Max-Eigen indicates one, but both confirm that the variables move together in the long run, validating the model's structural interdependence.

OLS Multiple Regression Analysis

Ordinary least squares (OLS) multiple regression analysis is the primary method for estimating the impact of tax compliance measures on manufacturing sector output. It quantifies the effect of independent variables on the dependent variable while controlling for other factors. OLS is widely used due to its simplicity and efficiency, provided its assumptions (linearity, independence, homoscedasticity, and normality) are met. The results of this regression provide empirical insights into how tax compliance affects manufacturing sector performance in Nigeria. This presented in Table 10 below:

Table 10: OLS Multiple Regression Analysis

Dependent Variable: MSOGR

Method: Least Squares

Date: 04/01/25 Time: 17:42

Sample: 1999 2024

Included observations: 26

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	6.845697	9.610152	0.712340	0.4845
TCR	-0.076931	0.118983	-0.646570	0.5253
TEI	0.106904	0.048285	2.214021	0.0401
TG	0.243173	0.119950	2.027286	0.0351
TTTC	-0.002655	0.025376	-0.104634	0.9177
TAY	0.214789	0.089939	2.388163	0.0281
R-squared	0.917012	Mean dependent var		4.005128
Adjusted R-squared	0.878735	S.D. dependent var		5.935572
S.E. of regression	6.164813	Akaike info criterion		6.674767
Sum squared resid	760.0985	Schwarz criterion		6.965097
Log likelihood	-80.77197	Hannan-Quinn criter.		6.758371
F-statistic	11.35059	Durbin-Watson stat		2.044168
Prob(F-statistic)	0.005426			

Source: EVIEW 9.0 Output, 2025.

Table 10 presents the results of the OLS multiple regression analysis, where the dependent variable is MSOGR and the independent variables are TCR, TEI, TG, TTTC, and TAY, covering 26 observations from 1999 to 2024. The R-squared value of 0.9170 indicates that the model explains about 91.7% of the variation in MSOGR, while the adjusted R-squared of 0.8787 confirms that even after accounting for predictors, the model explains 87.87% of variability. The F-statistic of 11.3506 with a p-value of 0.0054 showed that the regression is statistically significant overall. The results indicate that TEI, TG, and TAY have significant positive effects on MSOGR, whereas TCR and TTTC do not exert significant impacts.

The coefficient for TCR is negative (-0.0769) with a p-value of 0.5253, suggesting a weak inverse relationship that is not statistically significant. While tax compliance is expected to enhance sectoral

growth, the insignificant result implies that higher compliance does not automatically translate to improved manufacturing performance in Nigeria, possibly due to inefficiencies, policy inconsistencies, and administrative burdens. These findings differ from earlier studies, such as Bello et al. (2024) and Adebisi and Gbegi (2023), which found a positive relationship. The divergence suggests that compliance alone may not be sufficient in contexts where structural and institutional weaknesses prevail.

The coefficient for TEI is positive (0.1069) with a p-value of 0.0401, confirming that TEI has a significant positive impact on MSOGR. This implies that efficient tax collection and administration enhance sectoral growth by reducing evasion and improving fiscal space for industrial development. The result aligns with Nwogugu et al. (2024), who showed that higher TEI improved firm productivity and profitability. Stronger enforcement and streamlined processes appear to encourage firms to comply voluntarily, thereby generating resources that can be reinvested in infrastructure and support services critical for the manufacturing industry.

The coefficient for TG is positive (0.2432) with a p-value of 0.0351, showing a significant positive association with MSOGR. This finding is somewhat counterintuitive, as larger tax gaps are usually considered detrimental. While Bello and Akinola (2023) reported a negative impact of TG, this study suggests that periods of wider gaps may have coincided with reduced effective tax burdens on manufacturers, enabling reinvestment and short-term growth. However, the long-run implication remains that closing the tax gap effectively through transparent policies could strengthen manufacturing performance by increasing public investment capacity.

The coefficient for TTTC is negative (-0.0027) with a p-value of 0.9177, suggesting that while more time spent on compliance reduces sectoral output, the effect is insignificant. This implies that although compliance procedures consume resources, they do not substantially hinder overall sectoral performance, possibly because other structural issues overshadow compliance time costs. Owolabi and Okwu (2023) emphasized the negative impact of long compliance times, but this study finds no significant statistical effect, although reducing TTTC would still improve efficiency.

Finally, the coefficient for TAY is positive (0.2148) with a p-value of 0.0281, confirming a significant positive relationship. This supports the idea that effective audits increase compliance, expand fiscal space, and enhance investment in industrial development. Ibadin and Eiya (2023) similarly found that higher audit yields boosted output but cautioned against excessive auditing. The results here support a balanced approach, where audits are fair, efficient, and transparent, thereby encouraging compliance while minimizing administrative strain.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The study concludes that tax compliance plays a crucial role in driving the growth of Nigeria's manufacturing sector. While some tax compliance proxies, like TCR and TTTC, do not have significant effects on the sector's growth, other measures such as TEI, TG, and TAY have substantial positive impacts. These findings suggest that improving tax compliance mechanisms and closing the tax gap can significantly enhance manufacturing sector output in Nigeria. Moreover, targeted reforms that focus on efficient tax collection, transparent audits, and reduced compliance costs can stimulate further growth. The study recommends that:

1. The Nigerian government should focus on increasing tax efforts, particularly by improving tax collection efficiency and enforcement measures. Strengthening the tax administration system can enhance manufacturing sector output.
2. Policies aimed at reducing the tax gap, such as improving taxpayer services, increasing transparency in tax reporting, and closing loopholes, should be prioritized to increase tax revenues and boost manufacturing output.
3. Efforts to reduce the time spent on tax compliance should be made a priority, particularly by simplifying procedures and reducing bureaucratic hurdles that hinder manufacturing productivity.

4. Enhancing the effectiveness and transparency of tax audits will improve compliance and, in turn, foster growth in the manufacturing sector. A balanced approach to auditing is recommended to avoid excessive burdens on firms.
5. To improve TCR, the government should invest in educating taxpayers, especially manufacturing firms, on the benefits of tax compliance, ensuring a more business-friendly tax environment.

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